

Presenting News in Invenio

September 2014

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CERN openlab Summer Student Report 2014

Project Specification

Within the Invenio digital library platform,

1. Migrate the WebNews module, responsible for announcing news, from the current stable version of the software to the latest development version.
2. Introduce a web interface to allow the display and management of news for users and administrators .
3. Investigate alternative JavaScript libraries for news tooltips.

Abstract

The first step is discussing the process of learning and integrating the current WebNews code. Then there will be details on the new interface features that were added as well as the new tooltip functionality. There will also be information on the tooltip library and details on future work within this module.

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1 Introduction

The Invenio project was initially started for the purpose to manage documents within CERN, and its first instance is known as the CERN Document Server (CDS). CDS contains a wide variety of articles, publications, and multimedia documents. The Invenio digital library software platform offers ways to manage and organize that information and it allows users to search, categorize, and pull out information along with a variety of other features. Since its creation, Invenio has been picked up and is being used by over 30 institutions to manage documents.

The current version on Invenio has the functionality to display useful tooltips to the user and that functionality needs to be moved to the next version. However, the next version, called pu, uses new frameworks and technology standards that were not implemented in the current version.

The code is developed primarily in Python along with Javascript libraries for the frontend. The Flask framework is used for navigation, menus, and other architecture logistics. Redis is used as the key store cache and SQLAlchemy is used as the ORM tool to manipulate the database.

Finally, several new interfaces need to be created to manage and view news stories for administrators and to be linked to the tooltips.

2 The Invenio Standards

The first task of this projects was to adapt to the newest standards of Invenio and learn the frameworks and technologies to work with. This is the largest milestone for the proejct and took roughly half of the allotted 2 month time to complete.

2.1 Code Migration

The application itself is programmed in Python. It was build with a standard Model-View-Controller file system which makes each module simple for navigation. The database mapping was contained in the model.py classes, navigation controls were in the view.py, HTML was stored in the templates folders.

The original version of WebNews had a similar structure but not with the rigid standards. There were classes dedicated to the database models, view controllers, etc, but there did not seem to be a naming convention or specific, must-use standards. For this reason, a large portion of the original code had to be removed and rewritten. Ultimately, between using Flask for navigation , SQLAlchemy for database management, Redis for key value cache, the only code that was reused from the original was for checking full URLs and Jquery elements when creating tooltips.

The current database is structured around three tables. There was also several colums added to account for new features. Below is the build scripts to run for the updated tables which give an idea of the simple structure and dependencies:

```
CREATE TABLE `nwsSTORY` (  
  
  `id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,  
  
  `title` varchar(256) NOT NULL,  
  
  `body` text NOT NULL,  
  
  `created` timestamp NOT NULL DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP,  
  
  `document_status` varchar(45) NOT NULL COMMENT 'SHOW',  
  
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`)
```

```
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=72 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;
```

```
CREATE TABLE `nwsTAG` (  
  `id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,  
  `id_story` int(11) NOT NULL,  
  `tag` varchar(64) NOT NULL,  
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),  
  KEY `id_story` (`id_story`),  
  CONSTRAINT `nwsTAG_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`id_story`) REFERENCES  
  `nwsSTORY` (`id`)  
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=32 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;
```

```
CREATE TABLE `nwsTOOLTIP` (  
  `id` int(11) NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT,  
  `id_story` int(11) NOT NULL,  
  `body` varchar(512) NOT NULL,  
  `target_element` varchar(256) NOT NULL DEFAULT "",  
  `target_page` varchar(256) NOT NULL DEFAULT "",  
  PRIMARY KEY (`id`),  
  KEY `id_story` (`id_story`),  
  CONSTRAINT `nwsTOOLTIP_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY (`id_story`) REFERENCES  
  `nwsSTORY` (`id`)  
) ENGINE=InnoDB AUTO_INCREMENT=35 DEFAULT CHARSET=utf8;
```

Each news story record has 0 to many relationships with both tags and tooltips through an id association and that is how the redirect to the search page is done. Figure 1 shows

what the original tooltips looked like from the master version of Invenio. The only functionality was to display basic information using a custom Javascript library.

Figure 1. The original WebNews Tooltip

3 Enhancements

After the tooltip code was converted to the current standards the next task was to build the new interfaces. There were two interfaces that needed development.

3.1 New Interfaces

First, the News main search page. This page would be accessible to all users to search current news stories that were inside the nwsStory database table. The current search is simply based on a keyword search of the tags, title, and content of the article. Figure 2 shows the search interface at the time of this article.

Figure 2. Figure 2. The Current Search Interface for WebNews

This interface can be accessed either via the /news extension in the URL or from the dropdown menu. It uses SQLAlchemy to perform a search on the current database records and displays them using AJAX. When a user clicks on the news story it will display the full article. Additionally, the username of the author is displayed as well as all tags that are associated with that story. A user can click on any tag and the search page will display all stories that also have that tag. Additionally, when a user opens the search page it will display the most recent five news entries.

The next interface to be created was the admin interface which is accessible only to registered admins using Flask-Admin functionality. The interface is displayed through the URL extension /admin/news or from the toolbar admin option.

The first page for the admin work is the interfact to add a new news article. The inputs are in place to add the Title, Author, and Body. Next, a user must enter Tooltip information. The enter the text that will display inside the tooltip and then they must

enter the page and the name of the element for the tooltip to appear on. This interface is shown in Figure 2.

Then, once a page loads a script from the page_base template is run to check for tooltips on the elements of the page and displays them appropriately. This process is done using AJAX and JQuery. Ultimately, a user must know the page they wish to have the tooltip displayed and the name of the element to display it on.

Figure 3. The interface for adding new news stories

Figure 4. Figure 4. The interface for adding new news stories

For the edit page, the user is first presented with a search bar and the most recent 5 news stories as seen in Figure 3. The stories are searchable by keyword as well and once a user finds the story they want they can click on either the edit or delete icon.

Figure 5. The interface for finding and editing news stories. Also with WebNews Admin dropdown menu option to navigate to the page.

Once the Edit icon is clicked the user is taken to the interface to change the story. From this interface a user can edit any aspect of the current news story as well as add or remove more Tags and Tooltips. This interface is shown in Figure 4. When adding new tooltips or tags there is another interface as shown in Figure 5. Currently the Document Status field is set to only accept text fields for Show or Hide but it was designed with the possibility of new options which is why the database value is not a boolean. A hidden story will not appear in a general search.

INVENJO
admin

News Stories

Title

Body

CERN is the biggest particle physics laboratory in the world. More than 10,000 physicists from all around the world come to CERN to carry out experiments whose aim is to advance the understanding of the fundamentals of matter and the nature of our universe.

To explore these new frontiers of knowledge, CERN has developed a chain of accelerators, culminating in the LHC, has installed enormous particle detectors, and has pushed

Document Status

This field only accept SHOW or HIDE

ToolTips Add New+

Body	Target Element	Target Page	Edit	Delete
Photos from the Open Days to share? Upload them now on CDS!	\$("center)	http://cds.cern.ch/		
thttht	p	search.index		

Tag Add New+

TAG	Edit	Delete
CERN, Open Days 2013		
test		

Figure 6. The interface for editing existing stories

3.2 New Tooltip Library

One of the primary tasks for this project was deciding whether to continue to use the custom Javascript Library for the tooltips or to find a new library for the task. The tooltipster library was chosen because it was very lightweight and carried enough features for any possible future use. Additionally, and also the most important, it did not require a large structure change to how the current tooltips were implemented.

3.3 Tooltipster Implementation Details

The Tooltipster library is stored in the static/ folder on the webnews module. To call the tooltip within the application there is a script in the page_base.html which uses AJAX to check if the current page is within the database and if it is it checks if any of the element ids match as well. If there is a match it will display the tooltip. The code which calls for the tooltips is below and it can be found in templates/page_base.html:

```

<script type="text/javascript">
$(function() {
  $(document).on( "click", 'a.closetooltip', function() {
    $($ (this).attr("myparentinfo")).popover('hide')
  });
  $.getJSON( '/show_tooltips', {
    targetpage: [{ request.endpoint|tojson|safe }]
  }, function(data) {
    for(var i=0;i<data.tooltip.length;i++){
      VarforTooltip=$(data.tooltip[i].target_element );
      vardiv="<div id=" + data.tooltip[i].target_element + "_tip"><p> " + data.tooltip[i].body + "</p><p><a
style='color:#030367;' href='{{ url_for(config.CFG_WEBNEWS_SEARCH[1:]) }}/?id="+data.tooltip[i].id_story+">ReadMore</a> <a style='float:right;
color:#030367' class='closetooltip' href='#' myparentinfo="+data.tooltip[i].target_element+" >Dismiss</a></p></div>";
      $('#ToolTipData').append($(vardiv));
      $(VarforTooltip).popover({
        content:vardiv,
        trigger : "manual",
        html:true,
        placement : "bottom"
      }).show(function(){
        $(this).popover('show');
      });
    }
  });
});
</script>

```

The code calls the /show_tooltips functionality and then sets up the appropriate Read More and Dismiss links.

4 Future Work

The potential future work on WebNews is high because of its open source nature. It allows customization to be done depending on what is desired. Like every module in Invenio, because of the simple architecture it is simple for a user to make their own enhancements.

Past the point of the current implementation there is several places that could use immediate updates. First, the search is just a simple keyword match and depending on the number of records that will quickly become inadequate.

Additionally, hidden stories still appear if there is a tooltip linking to them. Whether or not this should apply still needs to be worked out and then implemented. Also, the current program does not have any paging implemented and when it gets to a point that there are many news announcements it would be ideal to implement that.

5 Conclusions

For this project a useful tooltip was migrated to the newest version of Invenio as well as several new interfaces were created using standards that are consistent with the next release.

The project was developed in Python using Flask, JavaScript, SQLAlchemy, and Redis. The programming standards follow with the rest of the project and many useful technologies have been learned. Plus, two useful interfaces were also developed to add additional features to the module

6 References

<http://iamceege.github.io/tooltipster/>